

Instagram Advertising Influencers and Customer Engagement among Undergraduate University Students in Port Harcourt

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Abstract

This study investigated the role of Instagram advertising influencers in shaping electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) among undergraduate students in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The study adopted perceived interactivity and hedonic content as dimensions of Instagram advertising influencers. Using a purposive and convenience sampling approach, data were collected through an online survey administered via SurveyMonkey to 400 students across three major universities in Port Harcourt, with 380 valid responses returned. Measurement scales were adapted from established literature, and reliability analysis confirmed adequate internal consistency. The findings reveal that Instagram influencers significantly influence consumer engagement and eWOM. Perceived interactivity was shown to enhance conversational exchanges, and improve brand advocacy, while hedonic content amplified experiential value, enjoyment, and emotional resonance, which in turn stimulated positive eWOM. The study concludes that Instagram influencers play a key role in shaping electronic word of mouth among university students in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria through perceived interactivity and hedonic content. The study recommends the need for Instagram influencers to design interactive, easy-to-use brand communication techniques, encourage user-generated content, and balance hedonic elements with informative value to sustain trust and long-term engagement.

Keywords: Consumer Engagement, Electronic Word-of-Mouth (eWOM), Hedonic Content, Instagram Influencers, and Perceived Interactivity.

1.1 Introduction

The rise of social media has revolutionized the advertising industry which is mainly driven by steady digital transformation, and significant alteration of how brand interact with their customers. In Nigeria, the traditional advertising channels (television, radio, and print) are being speedily displaced by the dynamic digital platforms. These digital platforms are more robust, and interactive with multiple functions and features to attract and sustain audience engagement. Among these platforms, Instagram has emerged as a prominent arena for brand–consumer interaction, particularly through the use of advertising influencers (De Veirman, Cauberghe, & Hudders, 2017). Instagram’s visual-centric and mobile-friendly architecture, along with its vast user base of over 1 billion globally active users, makes it especially appealing to young audiences (Statista, 2023; WordStream, 2019).

In Nigerian, the population of university students are predominantly Gen Z and Millennials and represent a peculiar demographic that exhibits high digital literacy, constant social media engagement, and susceptibility to influencer-based messaging (Ogande & Tsegysu, 2025). Hence, influencer marketers seize their parasocial relationships to developed and build followership, enabled by perceived expert opinion, and lifestyle role models. By strategically posting branded content, influencers aim to subtly shape the purchase intentions and attitudes of their audiences (Abidin, 2016; Boerman, 2020) which overtime affect customer engagement. According to Hollebeek, Glynn, and Brodie, (2014), customer engagement is the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral investment individuals make in brand interactions online.

Recent studies reveal that Instagram influencers increase customer engagement through perceived interactivity, visual authenticity, and narrative appeal (Jin & Phua, 2014; Casaló, Flavián, & Ibáñez-Sánchez, 2018). However, the extent to which customer engagement on Instagram leads to electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) remains under-researched in Nigerian. context. While global literature affirms that influencer-driven marketing often correlates with favorable consumer responses, the underlying mechanisms of engagement in emerging markets like Nigeria demand localized exploration (Casaló, Flavián, & Ibáñez-Sánchez, 2020). Research (Lou & Yuan, 2019; Djafarova & Trofimenko, 2019) suggests that influencer credibility and content authenticity are strong predictors of e-WOM, particularly among Gen Z consumers who value transparency and personal relevance.

In Nigeria, Ogande and Tsegysu (2025) demonstrate that Instagram influencers can stimulate up to 18% more behavioral engagement among university students; yet, the translation of such interactions into voluntary brand endorsement remains uncertain. Additionally, Adeyemi and Ogunyemi (2023) found that while students frequently interact with influencer posts, the

motivational drivers behind subsequent e-WOM are complex, influenced by cultural trust dynamics and platform literacy. Thus, this study addresses a fundamental literature gap by examining the extent to which Instagram advertising influencers, through perceived interactivity and perceived hedonic content, influence customer engagement and subsequently facilitate electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) among undergraduate students.

2.1 Theoretical Foundation

This study is conceptually grounded in two complementary theoretical lenses: the Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT) by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch (1974), and the Persuasion Knowledge Model (PKM) by Friestad and Wright (1994). According to the UGT, media audiences are rational, and self-aware agents who actively and voluntarily select media content to fulfill psychological, emotional, and social gratifications. In this regard, Instagram offers variety of visual aesthetic, and social interactivity that caters to hedonic, relational, and informational needs, especially among digitally immersed youth populations (Sheldon & Bryant, 2016; Lee, Hur, & Watkins, 2021). Hence, engagement is driven by an internal gratification logic consistent with UGT's core propositions. On the other hand, the Persuasion Knowledge Model posit that consumers detect, interpret, and resist persuasion attempts. PKM argues that the realization that a communication attempt is commercially persuaded activate their persuasion knowledge to critically evaluate the content (Boerman, Willemsen, & Van Der Aa, 2017). Studies (Evans, Phua, Lim, & Jun, 2017; Stubb & Colliander, 2019) found that undisclosed or poorly disclosed sponsorships can provoke consumer skepticism, reduce credibility, and ultimately hinder engagement, and may cause disengagement, message discounting, or negative word-of-mouth.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Belanche, Flavián, and Pérez-Rueda, 2019; Wong (2014); Wei, Peng, and Chou (2015); Seo and Park (2018); Hollebeek, Jaakkola, and Alexander, (2018).

2.2 Review of Related Literature

2.2.1 Customer Engagement (CE)

In contemporary marketing scholarship, customer engagement (CE) has emerged as a multidimensional construct integral to understanding consumer-brand dynamics, particularly in digital contexts (Hollebeek, Clark, & Macky, 2022). Yet, the definitional clarity of CE remains a contested issue, prompting scholars to disentangle its behavioral, cognitive, and emotional underpinnings (Clark et al., 2020; Rosado-Pinto & Loureiro, 2020). A widely accepted premise is that CE represents a customer's voluntary and interactive connection with a brand, encompassing activities beyond transactional exchanges (Vivek, Beatty, Dalela, & Morgan, 2014).

Recent empirical studies affirm that CE is shaped by customer experiences with computer-mediated environments, particularly social platforms like Instagram, where co-creation and emotional investment are intensified (Kritzing & Petzer, 2020). According to Abdel-Gayed et al. (2023), customer engagement is now recognized as a key driver of satisfaction and business performance, with significant implications for loyalty and word-of-mouth (WOM). Within this digital ecosystem, CE is best understood as a process with three interlinked dimensions: (1) cognitive engagement, referring to consumer attentiveness and absorption with a brand; (2) emotional engagement, which reflects positive affective states; and (3) behavioral engagement, involving actions such as commenting, sharing, and tagging (Leckie, Nyadzayo, & Johnson, 2016; Schaufeli et al., 2002; Hollebeek & Chen, 2014).

For instance, Hajjaliakbari and Babaei (2025) demonstrated that influencer-led Instagram campaigns enhanced both emotional and behavioral engagement in younger audiences. Likewise, Carlson, Wyllie, Rahman, and Meyer (2018) found that emotionally charged content increased behavioral outcomes such as repeat interactions and product referrals. Pansari and Kumar (2017) extend this logic, suggesting that indirect engagement, including e-WOM and customer feedback loops, may hold even greater value than immediate transactional outcomes. This is supported by Jeyanthi, Cvetkoska, and Kitanovikj (2024), who argue that behavioral engagement, particularly in digital sports and entertainment brands, predicts long-term consumer affiliation more effectively than mere satisfaction scores. In this study, we adopt Hollebeek, Glynn, and Brodie's (2014) definition of CE as "positively valenced brand-related cognitive, emotional and behavioral activity during or related to consumer/brand interactions" (p. 154).

2.3 Electronic Word-of-Mouth

Electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) has emerged as a pivotal mechanism in digital consumer behavior, shaping brand reputation, influencing decision-making, and extending engagement beyond the point of purchase. Hennig-Thurau et al. (2004) offered a foundational definition,

viewing eWOM as “any positive or negative statement made by potential, actual, or former customers about a product or company, made available to a multitude of people and institutions via the Internet.” This perspective emphasizes the interpersonal reach and sentiment-driven nature of digital communication. More recently, Rosario, Sotgiu, Valck, and Bijmolt (2016) re-conceptualized eWOM as “a multidimensional construct encompassing message valence, volume, credibility, and reach,” with each dimension having distinct implications for marketing outcomes. The latter framework introduces a more actionable typology that allows for empirical scrutiny of how eWOM functions in algorithmic and influencer-driven contexts. Given the multidimensionality and measurement utility of this model, the current study adopts Rosario et al.'s (2016) conceptualization, which more effectively captures the scope of eWOM in influencer-mediated environments such as Instagram, especially among digitally active demographics like university students.

2.4 Instagram Advertising Influencers

Social media has transformed marketing communication from linear, one-way messaging to interactive and participatory exchanges where audiences actively shape brand narratives (Jung, 2017). As a result, Instagram influencers have emerged as key opinion leaders, and have cultivated large digital followings through lifestyle-centered, visually curated content (Abidin, 2016; De Veirman et al., 2017). Their persuasive power lies in perceived authenticity, expertise, and relatability, which stimulate engagement through likes, shares, and comments while encouraging parasocial relationships with followers (Casaló et al., 2018; De Veirman, Hudders, & Nelson, 2022). Studies (Lou & Yuan, 2019; Djafarova & Trofimenko, 2019) indicate that follower engagement with influencers translates into outcomes such as electronic word-of-mouth, brand affinity, and purchase intention. Instagram influencers leverage their social capital, credibility, and relatability to co-create brand narratives with audiences, thereby amplifying visibility, stimulating electronic word-of-mouth, and shaping consumer attitudes and purchase intentions (Djafarova & Trofimenko, 2019; Lou & Yuan, 2019). In this study, an Instagram influencer is a digital opinion leader who creates lifestyle-centered, visually curated content that creates parasocial relationships with followers while entrenching brand messages in ways perceived as authentic and trustworthy (Abidin, 2016; Casaló, Flavián, & Ibáñez-Sánchez, 2018; De Veirman, Hudders, & Nelson, 2022).

2.4.1 Perceived Interactivity and Customer Electronic Word-of-Mouth

Perceived interactivity refers to an individual's subjective sense of reciprocal communication, responsiveness, and control while engaging with media content (Liu & Shrum, 2002). On platforms like Instagram, it represents the dynamic interface between influencer-generated content and follower participation. The interactivity motivated by stories, and live sessions contributes to cognitive absorption, emotional alignment, and ultimately, behavioral loyalty (Jiang et al., 2021;

Pongpaew, Speece, & Tiangsoongnern, 2017). In essence, the psychological closeness created through real-time interaction bridges the traditional gap between influencer and consumer, creating a personalized marketing ecosystem (Alalwan, 2022). Such dialogic affordances are no longer peripheral but core mechanisms for building parasocial relationships and stimulating e-WOM, particularly among Gen Z consumers in digitally saturated contexts (Ogande & Tseyu, 2025).

Contemporary literature affirms that perceived interactivity is a catalyst for engagement intensity, trust formation, and utilitarian value realization (Jeon, Jang, & Barrett, 2017; Yoo, Lee, & Park, 2010). Lin and Chang (2018) argue that it manifests in two domains: human-to-human and human-to-content interaction. These domains fuel affective and behavioral engagement, encouraging users to comment, share, and endorse brand messages (Dessart, 2017). Moreover, the effectiveness of influencer marketing lies not merely in the influencer's reach, but in their ability to spark conversational momentum and foster co-creation of value through social exchange (Demangeot & Broderick, 2016; Casaló, Flavián, & Guinalú, 2011). As interactivity heightens, users become less passive and more participatory, thus deepening brand immersion and laying fertile ground for engagement-based outcomes like brand advocacy and e-WOM (Brodie et al., 2013; Hollebeek et al., 2018). Based on the foregoing, this study hypothesizes that:

H₁: There is no significant relationship between perceived hedonic content and electronic word-of-mouth.

2.4.2 Perceived Hedonic Content and Electronic Word-of-Mouth

The concept of hedonic value was proposed by Hirschman and Holbrook (1982) with emphasis on pleasure from purchasing or using services (Holbrook, 1996). Perceived hedonic content refers to the sensory and emotional gratification derived from consuming digital media, particularly on platforms such as Instagram. Unlike utilitarian content that fulfills functional needs, hedonic content appeals to aesthetics, pleasure, and emotional resonance (Valenzuela-Gálvez & González-Benito, 2024). Hedonic value is defined as the value that a customer receives in terms of subjective experiences of fun and playfulness (Holbrook & Hirschman, 1982; Babin, Darden & Griffin, 1994). Within the Instagram social network, hedonic value of a post refers to the degree to which a post or an update is considered to be enjoyable, filled with emotions, and entertaining to the pleasure of the followers. According to Seo and Park (2018), social media followers who use social media for hedonistic reasons are considered to be those looking for fun and pleasure, and virtual communities are organized according to these interests for them.

The interrelatedness between hedonic value and customer behavior modification has witnessed increased debates over the years. Recent scholarship finds that short-form video content embedded with sound and emotional cues significantly heightens perceived hedonic value, ultimately boosting customer engagement on Instagram (Valenzuela-Gálvez et al., 2024). Prior studies have

suggested a link between hedonic values, purchase intentions, and continued use intention (Ozturk, Nusair, Okumus, & Hua, 2016; Juaneda-Ayensa, Mosquera, & Murillo, 2016; Park & Ha, 2016). Evidences suggest that hedonic content can have an impact on attitudes and WOM (Berger & Schwartz, 2011; Kim, Ratneshwar, & Thorson, 2017). Moreover, hedonic gratification has been found to moderate the relationship between influencer content and behavioral intention, especially among younger users for whom entertainment is a key driver of media use (Casaló et al., 2018; Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017). According to De Veirman, Hudders, and Nelson (2022), hedonic experiences enhance feelings of enjoyment, admiration, and brand closeness, and catalyze deeper engagement and virality through shares, likes, and eWOM. This study defines perceived hedonic content as the extent to which Instagram influencer content delivers emotional pleasure, visual stimulation, and entertainment value to university students, thereby reinforcing their digital connection with the brand and stimulating interactive engagement. Hence, this study hypothesizes that:

H₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived hedonic content and electronic word-of-mouth.

3.0 Methodology

The sample responses were drawn from Port Harcourt, a major city in the south-south region of Nigeria. The justification for this decision is on the account that Port Harcourt has a major concentration of Universities (University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University). Respondents were conveniently and purposively approached through their respective Student Union Government (SUG) secretariat. The strength of the convenience sampling technique lies in its ability to generate a large pool of respondents in a relatively short time (Hair, Bush & Ortinau 2006). According to Asika (1991) a researcher may be guided by what he considers typical cases which are the most likely to provide him with the requisite data or information. In this case the researcher is at leisure to determine the appropriate respondents for the study. Questionnaire was the major research instrument used for the collection of data for this study. Also, the researcher determined those with relevant information by choosing them on purpose. All measures used in instrument design were adopted and modified from existing scales to ensure validity and reliability. The researcher conducted online survey monkey involving 400 participants. The strength of the convenience sampling technique lies in its ability to generate a large pool of respondents in a relatively short time (Hair et al., 2006) who are abreast with the pertinent information sought for. On this note, 400 copies of questionnaire were dispatched to students' using the survey monkey approach as 400 students contacted were provided by the SUG. Out of the 400 copies distributed, 380 were filled and returned. The selected samples for the study are the accurate representative of the population. Saunders, Lewis and Thonrhill (2009) suggested that sample needs to be as representative and accurate as possible where it will be used to

generalize about the total population. Reliability analysis shows the value of Cronbach’s alpha as 0.819 for perceived interactivity, 0.889 for perceived hedonic content and 0.806 for social electronic word of mouth which lies between the accepted range of 0.5 to 0.9. Nunnally (1978) recommended that scales maintained adequate internal consistency if it exceeds the .70 criterion. Hence, the questionnaire administered has enough reliability to proceed further for analyses.

4.1 Data Analysis and Results

4.2 Bivariate analyses using Multiple Regression

4.2.1 Model One

H1: There is no significant relationship between Perceived Interactivity and Electronic Word of Mouth among University Students in Port Harcourt.

Table 4.1: Regression Analysis showing the relationship between Perceived Interactivity and Electronic Word of Mouth

Model Summary table with columns: Model, R, R Square, Adjusted R Square, Std. Error of the Estimate

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Interactivity

Table 4.2: ANOVA (First Model)

ANOVA table with columns: Model, Sum of Squares, Df, Mean Square, F, Sig.

a. Dependent Variable: Electronic Word of Mouth

b. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Interactivity

Table 4.3: Coefficients (First Model)

Coefficients table with columns: Model, Unstandardized Coefficients (B, Std. Error), Standardized Coefficients (Beta), T, Sig.

Regression Model: SEW = 3.119 + 0.892PI

The regression analysis in Model One tested the relationship between perceived interactivity and electronic word of mouth. Results from the model summary (R² = 0.738, Adjusted R² = 0.702) indicate that perceived interactivity explains approximately 73.8% of the variance in SEW, while the remaining 26.2% is attributed to other factors not included in the model. The ANOVA results confirm the model’s statistical significance (F = 66.840, p < 0.001), thereby demonstrating a strong predictive relationship. The coefficient analysis further reveals that perceived interactivity (β = 0.699, p < 0.001) has a positive and significant effect on SEW. Accordingly, the null hypothesis (H1) is rejected, suggesting that higher levels of perceived interactivity significantly enhance electronic word of mouth among undergraduate students in Port Harcourt.

4.2.2 Model Two

H2: There is no significant relationship between Perceived Hedonic Content and Electronic Word of Mouth among University Students in Port Harcourt.

Table 4.4: Regression Analysis showing the relationship between Perceived Hedonic Content and Electronic Word of Mouth

Model Summary table with columns: Model, R, R Square, Adjusted R Square, Std. Error of the Estimate. Row 1: .816a, .666, .637, 20.61728

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Hedonic Content

Table 4.5: ANOVA (Second Model)

ANOVA table with columns: Model, Sum of Squares, Df, Mean Square, F, Sig. Rows: Regression (23708.417, 1, 14711.039, 34.398, .000b), Residual (19294.525, 379, 351.431), Total (28266.251, 380)

a. Dependent Variable: Electronic Word of Mouth

b. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Hedonic Content

Table 4.6: Coefficients (Second Model)

Coefficients table with columns: Model, Unstandardized Coefficients (B, Std. Error), Standardized Coefficients (Beta), t, Sig. Rows: (Constant) (1.739, 4.850, .392), Perceived Hedonic Content (.527, .175, .888, 3.778, .000)

Regression Model: SEW = 1.739 + 0.527PHC

Model Two examined the relationship between perceived hedonic content and electronic word of mouth. The findings demonstrate that perceived hedonic content accounts for 66.6% of the variance in SEW ($R^2 = 0.666$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.637$). This indicates the existence of a strong explanatory power. The ANOVA results further confirm the significance of the model ($F = 34.398$, $p < 0.001$). The coefficient analysis shows that perceived hedonic content ($\beta = 0.888$, $p < 0.001$) significantly and positively predicts electronic word of mouth. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_2) is also rejected. This suggests that hedonic content, which enhances enjoyment and entertainment, strongly contributes to the generation of electronic word of mouth among undergraduate students.

5.1 Discussion of Findings

5.1.1 Perceived Interactivity and Customer Electronic Word-of-Mouth

The results of this study confirm that perceived interactivity significantly predicts electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) among undergraduate students in Port Harcourt. Studies (Demangeot & Broderick, 2016; Casaló, Flavián, & Guinalú, 2011) emphasized that the effectiveness of influencer marketing lies in the capacity to generate conversational momentum and co-create value through interactive exchanges. Interactivity reduces consumer passivity by encouraging dialogue, personalized exchanges, and mutual responsiveness, which deepen brand immersion and stimulate eWOM (Brodie et al., 2013; Hollebeek et al., 2018). Likes, comments, shares, and story polls strengthen bonds within the Instagram community and enhances bonds and perceived authenticity which increases the likelihood that audiences will amplify brand messages across their networks. The finding that perceived interactivity explains a substantial proportion of variance in eWOM (73.8%) thus reinforces the argument that perceived interactivity is a major driver of e-WoM.

5.1.2 Perceived Hedonic Content and Electronic Word-of-Mouth

Similarly, the study establishes that perceived hedonic content significantly influences eWOM, which accounts for 66.6% of variance. This supports prior evidence that hedonic value enhances enjoyment, shapes attitudes, and stimulates word-of-mouth behaviors (Berger & Schwartz, 2011; Kim, Ratneshwar, & Thorson, 2017). Previous research (Casaló et al., 2018; Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017) submitted that hedonic gratifications such as entertainment, aesthetic appeal, and emotional resonance moderated the impact of influencer content on consumer behavior, particularly among younger demographics for whom media use is driven by pleasure and escapism. In line with De Veirman, Hudders, and Nelson (2022), this study finds that hedonic experiences enhance enjoyment, admiration, and brand closeness, which in turn catalyze social sharing and eWOM. Collectively, these findings affirm that both interactivity and hedonic content represent key levers through which Instagram influencers influence e-WoM.

5.2 Conclusion

This study considered two dimensions of Instagram advertising influencers on customer engagement among undergraduate students in Port Harcourt. This study has demonstrated that Instagram influencers play a key role in shaping electronic word of mouth among university students in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria through perceived interactivity and hedonic content. The findings confirmed that interactivity enhance consumer engagement and also amplifies conversational exchanges and brand advocacy. Similarly, hedonic content enhances the experiential dimension of influencer–follower interactions, and creates enjoyment and emotional resonance that stimulate positive eWOM.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Instagram influencers acting as brand ambassadors should adopt interactive and user-friendly brand communication techniques that drive consumers' intention to engage and participate in electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM).
2. Brands should encourage consumers to create, like, and share interactive content with peers on the platform.
3. Influencers and brands should design Instagram brand pages that combine ease of navigation, interactivity, and hedonic value for improved user experiences.
4. Interactive and hedonic strategies should be deployed to enhance consumers' cognitive understanding of the brand.
5. Instagram influencer should balance hedonic content with informative value to ensure that brand messages are not overshadowed by purely entertaining elements.

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